

DURABILITY OF SODA—LIME—SILICATE GLASSES. PART II

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The effect of composition on the durability of glass has been studied. It has been shown that two or more glasses of different compositions can possess identical durability. The possibility of theoretically calculating the durability of a glass (in terms of H_2SO_4 value) from a knowledge of its composition has been attempted.

In a previous communication (Chowdhury and Das-Gupta, this *Journal*, 1947, **24**, 477), a study of the effect of substitution of known amounts of a given constituent upon durabilities of a series of 'like' glasses was made. The relation between chemical durability and composition of different series of 'like' glasses was also represented graphically, and the method of representing such a relation was illustrated there. Those curves indicate the possibility of obtaining identical durability for a number of glass compositions. This aspect of the problem was partly verified experimentally. The present paper embraces the following :

- (1) Further study of the effect of composition on durability.
- (2) To establish finally our finding that two or more glasses of different compositions can possess identical durability.
- (3) To explore the possibility of calculating, theoretically, the durability of a glass (expressed in terms of sulphuric acid value) from a knowledge of its composition.

Gelstharp and Parkinson (*Trans. Amer. Cer. Soc.*, 1914, **16**, 109) had made a systematic study in respect of compositions suitable for proper soda-lime-silicate glasses and they had represented their data by a tri-axial diagram. With a view to studying further the relation between composition and durability, the compositions have been so selected that they are well within the range specified for transparent glass proper, including technical glass. The durabilities of glasses produced were determined by 'Powder test' (Faraday, *Phil. Trans.*, 1830, p.49 ; Pelouze, *Compt. rend.*, 1856, **43**, 117 ; Mylius and Foerster, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 1092 ; *Z. Instrum. Kunde*, 1889, **9**, 120 ; Hagmaier, *Met. Chem. Eng.*, 1917, **16**, 604 ; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1919, **169**, 335 ; Peddle, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1920, **4**, 3, 299 ; 1921, **5**, 72, 195).

The relation between composition and durability of different 'like' glasses (including those in Table III, part I) has been shown in Fig.1. In order to establish our second object, compositions, corresponding to different sulphuric acid values, have been computed from the curves of Fig.1. Table V shows such computed compositions and the sulphuric acid values actually found out.

The curves of Fig.1 may be utilised to draw contour lines. Thus, if the set of compositions, corresponding to a particular acid value, be plotted in the phase equilibrium diagram of the ternary system $Na_2O-CaO-SiO_2$ after Morey and Bowen (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1925, **9**, 226), these will be represented by several points. A line joining these points would represent compositions having the same sulphuric acid value. Similarly, for different sets corresponding lines may be drawn. From analogy with iso-property curves or 'contour' lines like isotherms (Morey and Bowen, *loc. cit.*), and Isokoms (Washburn, Shelton and Libman,

Univ. Ill. Eng. Expt. Station Bull., 1924, p.140), these curves (Fig.2) have been designated as iso-durability curves.

It is well known that some of the physical properties of glass are additive in character. No serious attempt has been made with a view to correlating chemical durability of glass, in terms of sulphuric acid value, with its composition except, however, by empirical formulæ. It appears that Lyle, Horak and Sharp (*J. Amer. Cer. Soc.*, 1936, **19**, 142) made a study of the effect of alumina on chemical durability of glass. The results obtained with glasses containing Na_2O , CaO , Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 were represented by the formula :

$\log D = -6.427 + 5.89 \log (N+A) - 0.654 (\log A)$, in which D represents the durability in terms of the number of c.c. of $0.02N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ required to neutralise the alkali extracted from 10g. of glass, and N and A represent the percentages of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 respectively. This formula, however, gives the maximum effect in respect of durability. As stated earlier, the chemical durability of glass is a function of the percentages of the different constituent oxides, and as such, there can be no reason why these cannot be linked up theoretically. Thus, from analogy with other physical properties, this relation may be represented roughly by means of a formula of the type :

$D = aX + bY + cZ$, in which D represents durability in terms of sulphuric acid value and X, Y and Z represent the percentages of SiO_2 , CaO and Na_2O respectively and 'a', 'b' and 'c' represent the corresponding factors. The values for the factors 'a', 'b' and 'c' have been worked out by solving different sets of three equations of each and taking the mean values. These equations are framed by substituting the actual values of D, X, Y and Z from Table IV. It will be seen that the calculated values for 'a' and 'b' are negative. This supports the fact that silica and lime impart increased durability in glass. Also, the value for 'b' is more negative than that for 'a', and this is in agreement with the observation that substitution of silica by a diabasic oxide, the alkali remaining constant, improves durability (*Enss, Glastechn. Ber.*, 1928, **5**, 1). The values for 'c' is highly positive and this should naturally be the case.

EXPERIMENTAL

The procedure adopted for melting, plaining, and annealing the glasses of different compositions was the same as on the previous occasion (Part I, *loc. cit.*). Five series of glass batches were melted, and as usual, the percentage of silica in each series was kept constant, while successive amounts of Na_2O were replaced by lime. The sources of raw materials for glasses were different. Table I shows the purity of raw materials used and Table II gives the compositions of the glasses melted.

TABLE I

Material.	Percentage of						
	SiO_2 .	Fe_2O_3 .	Al_2O_3 .	CaO .	MgO .	Na_2CO_3 .	Loss.
Sand (Series D & E)	97.96	Trace	1.59	—	—	—	0.47
„ (rest)	97.44	0.51	1.24	0.32	—	—	0.46
Lime (Series D & E)	1.39	2.04	0.30	69.87	Trace	—	26.30
„ (rest)	2.01	0.41	4.90	71.51	Trace	—	20.98
Heavy soda-ash (D & E)	—	—	—	S. trace	S. trace	90.87	9.05
„ (rest)	0.35	—	—	0.08	S. trace	90.85	8.60

TABLE II

Batch No.	Batch mixture (in g.)			Percentage composition			Remarks.
	Sand.	Soda.	Lime.	SiO ₂ .	Na ₂ O.	CaO.	
Series B ₁							
22	71.83	22.58	25.21	70	12	18	Clear, slight scum
23	71.83	24.46	23.80	70	13	17	Do
24	71.83	26.34	22.41	70	14	16	Very clear melt
25	71.83	28.23	20.98	70	15	15	Do
Series D							
26	76.56	28.32	14.31	75	15	10	Slight devitrification
27	76.56	23.50	17.89	75	12.5	12.5	Do
Series E							
28	69.41	37.63	17.17	68	20	12	Bright melt
29	69.41	33.87	20.03	68	18	14	Do
30	69.41	31.79	23.61	68	15.5	16.5	Clear melt
31	69.41	29.73	25.04	68	14.5	17.5	Do
32	69.41	24.46	27.19	68	13	19	Do
33	69.41	22.60	28.02	68	12	20	Scum formation
34	69.41	18.81	31.46	68	10	22	Thick scum with stone formation.
Series E ₁							
35	69.86	26.34	25.21	68	14	18	Clear melt
36	69.86	28.23	23.80	68	15	17	Very clear melt
37	69.86	30.10	22.41	68	16	16	Do
38	69.86	31.98	20.98	68	17	15	Do
Series F							
39	67.81	26.34	27.98	66	14	20	Perfectly clear
40	67.81	28.23	26.56	66	15	19	Do
41	67.81	30.1	25.21	66	16	18	Do
42	67.81	31.98	23.80	66	17	17	Do

It may be pointed out that in Table II minute traces of silica, lime, etc., derived from sources other than specified, have not been taken into account.

Ordinarily, during founding of glass, the composition varies to some extent. The extent of such variation will be clear from Table III, showing complete analyses of the three different samples.

TABLE III

Sample.	Percentage composition expected					Percentage composition found				
	SiO ₂ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	Na ₂ O.	SiO ₂ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	Na ₂ O.
1.	68.23	2.05	0.46	17.65	11.61	68.63	2.2	0.52	17.41	11.12
2.	66.43	1.96	0.43	15.71	15.47	66.87	2.24	0.46	15.65	14.7
3.	64.49	1.93	0.42	16.69	16.47	65.06	2.00	0.50	16.49	15.9

The results of powder test have been incorporated in Table IV and the graphic relation has been shown in Fig. 1. As mentioned before, Fig. 2 shows similar relation for all glasses, inclusive of those included in Table III, Part I (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE IV

Batch No.	H ₂ SO ₄ value.	Batch No.	H ₂ SO ₄ value.	Batch No.	H ₂ SO ₄ value.
	Series B ₁ .		Series E.		Series E ₁ .
22	160	28	800	35	161.4
23	181.9	29	465	36	371.6
24	218.1	30	400	37	415.7
25	299.2	32	112	38	436.2
		33	82		
	Series D				Series F.
26	368			39	321.7
27	150			40	428.8
				41	470.9
				42	496.1

Fig 1

From Fig. 1 several compositions corresponding to different sulphuric acid values have been computed. The results of powder test, made in respect of these glasses, have been incorporated in Table V. It will be seen that the experimental values are in close agreement with the expected values. This establishes our finding regarding the possibility of preparing iso-durable glasses.

TABLE V

Computed compositions(%)			Sulphuric acid value.	
SiO ₂ .	Na ₂ O.	CaO.	Expected.	Found.
70	13.5	17.5	200	196.0
73	13.25	13.75	200	198.2
74	14	12	200	196.5
70	15	15	300	303
73	16.3	10.7	300	308
74	15	11	300	290
75	14.5	10.5	300	310
73	17.2	9.8	500	510
74	16	10	500	508
75	15.6	9.4	500	503

As explained earlier, Fig. 1 also furnishes the possibility of computing compositions for iso-durable curves. These points have been plotted in the phase equilibrium diagram of the ternary system, Na₂O—CaO—SiO₂, after Morey and Bowen (*loc. cit.*) and Fig. 2 shows the actual dispositions of these curves.,

The question of linking up theoretically the durability of a glass with its composition has been but approximately solved. The calculated values agree with the expected values within certain range and up to a maximum of 15% Na₂O in the glass. In the formula, $D = aX + bY + cZ$, the influences of traces of MgO, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃, etc., have not been taken into account. This may be the reason why in almost every case the calculated

figure is higher than the actual values. If, however, the alkali content exceeds 15%, there is appreciable divergence between the calculated and the observed values. The worked out values for the factors 'a', 'b' and 'c', are respectively as -0.8, -9 and +30. Table VI embraces a few glass compositions, showing calculated and observed sulphuric acid values.

TABLE VI

SiO ₂	% Composition		Sulphuric acid value	
	CaO.	Na ₂ O	Observed.	Calculated. ($a = -0.8, b = -9$ & $c = 30$)
73	12	15	235	233
73	13	14	225	249
73	14	13	186	205
73	14.5	12.5	154	187.1
73	15.5	11.5	119	147
73	17	10	93	88
73	10.5	18.5	320	357.5
73	9.5	17.5	578	381
73	8.5	18.5	879	320
70	12.5	17.5	479	357
70	14	16	399	298
70	15	15	303	259
70	17.5	12.5	164	162
70	16	14	218	220
74	8.5	17.5	783	389
74	10	16	506	331
74	11	15	290	292
74	13.5	12.5	156	194.3

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